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Qualitative study on military and internal security operation in Nigeria: 2013-2023

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Abstract

The study examines military and internal security operation in Nigeria: 2013-2023. The study employed an exploratory approach and gathered data from secondary sources such as the Google and Google Scholar search engines, media, and academic and research groups that have conducted research on the subject. The study findings revealed that rural banditry, farmer and herders' conflicts, Boko-Haram, and succession of Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) were major internal security in Nigeria. Also, excessive use of force, arbitrary arrest, degrading treatment of citizens and extra judicial killings were the military mode of operation during internal security. The study findings also revealed that training, orientation, strategy and tactics, and equipment were the major challenges of the military during internal security operation. The study concludes that the military is generally abusive and engaged in numerous predatory activities that violate the human rights of the populace and further their sense of insecurity. Despite that, the military's acceptance as the most powerful organ of the state with the superior coercive force to suppress the threats and violence posed by armed groups. The study recommended among others that there is a need for an improvement in military control as regard to human rights abuses by engaging the National Human Rights Commission to handles or comparable tasks as, an independent military investigator who is focused on military abuse problems would be more helpful.

Keywords: Internal Security, Military, Operation.

Introduction

A state's principal role is to safeguard its population against external aggression as well as internal violence and unrest. In liberal democracies, the police are usually in charge of this (Bigo, 2000; Lioe, 2011). However, as violence erupts and the security situation deteriorates in Nigeria, as in many African countries, governments frequently rely on the military to restore order and calm (Howe, 2001). This is largely due to the police's inability to contain violent disputes, particularly when citizens' security is endangered by armed organizations (Nwolise, 2007; Omede, 2012). As a result, Baker (2010) contends that most African police units are not adequately equipped or educated to deal with the problems posed by armed groups and internal armed conflicts. As a result, the government is frequently forced to utilize the military in an internal role since it is the only state instrument with the necessary coercive capacity to suppress violence, disorder, or insurgency (Peterside, 2014). The ability to contain such violence is a challenge that many African countries face in the twenty-first century. This is especially true when disputes intensify and the country devolves into internal strife (Okumu & Ikelegbe, 2010). Numerous elements can be attributed to the causes of these violent conflicts in Africa (Gurr, Marshall & Khosla, 2000; Sarkees, Wayman & Singer, 2003). These include excessive wealth disparity, ethnic and religious divisions being manipulated and exploited, greed, and a lack of judicial procedures to address these concerns (Collier & Hoeffler, 2002, 2004). Other issues include the government's failure to provide fundamental public goods, frustrations stemming from the marginalization of minority ethnic groups, and citizens' inability to obtain economic, political, or social privileges in society. Armed organizations typically exploit these situations, with the bulk of them motivated by political goals, economic intent, and extremist religious doctrines (Fearon & Laitin, 2003; Vre, 2010).

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The growth of these armed groups in various forms is now playing a significant role in international politics and security sector changes in the twenty-first century (Vinci, 2008).

Armed groups are commonly used as spoilers or troublemakers in state-building and peace-building attempts (Schneckener, 2006). They endanger citizen security and the supply of public goods by leveraging existing complaints and disturbing states' essential operations, eroding their legitimacy (Stewart, 2002, 2004). This is especially true when they undertake coordinated attacks on civilian groups, essential infrastructure, or state forces and gain control of areas of a state (Thompson, 2014). As a result, states resort to the military to aid police in preserving domestic security and containing the risks posed by armed groups. Using the military for internal security operations (ISOPs), also known as military help to civil authority (MACA), has its own set of difficulties. One is the training of military troops, which is not suitable for employment in an internal societal role. The military's concentration is on defense, war, and the infliction of collective violence, as opposed to the police, whose primary duty is law enforcement (Harris, 2003; Weiss, 2012). The military tends to dominate in collaborative units or as hybrid security forces with police and other civilian organizations. This is most common in jurisdictions with no constabulary forces or gendarmeries. In terms of command and control, hybrid forces comprised of joint police and military units pose various challenges. Military sociologists and other security strategists regard the military as a crucial tool for conflict de-escalation in order to reinstall peace and order (Von Bredow, 2006). The deployment of the military in an internal role in society has become the norm in several African states because "when violence breaks out, policymakers and society at large believe that the military should be brought in" (José & Rasmussen, 1999). This is the scenario in Nigeria, where the military is continually deployed to tackle the threat posed by civil war and armed groups seeking to destabilize the government (Omede, 2012; Dambazau, 2014). It is against this background that the study interrogated the military and internal security operation in Nigeria

Concept of military

A military also referred to as the armed forces as a whole, is a well-equipped, well-organized organization that is mainly designed for combat. Its members can usually be recognized by their distinctive military uniforms, and it is typically approved and kept by a sovereign state. One or more military divisions, such as the army, navy, air force, space force, commandos, or coast guard, may make up this force. Defence of the state and its interests against exterior armed threats is typically described as the military's primary duty. In general usage, the words "armed forces" and "military" are frequently used interchangeably, but in formal usage, the terms "armed forces" and "military" can refer to both the military and other paramilitary forces of a nation. Unaffiliated with a recognized state, irregular military forces come in many different shapes. Despite sharing many characteristics with regular military forces, they are less frequently referred to as merely military.

The military of a country may operate as a distinct social subculture with its own infrastructure, including homes, utilities, schools, logistics, clinics, judicial services, food supply, finance, and banking. Beyond combat, the military may be used by the government for other authorized and unapproved purposes, such as countering threats to internal security, managing population growth, advancing political objectives, providing emergency services and reconstruction, safeguarding corporate economic interests, providing national honour guards, and responding to natural disasters (Mark, 2009). Military service is a career that predates written history itself (Jordan, Kiras, Lonsdale, Speller, Tuck, and Walton). (2016). The strength and prowess of ancient antiquity's war commanders are depicted in some of the most enduring artworks. One of the turning moments in Pharaoh Ramses II's rule was the Battle of Kadesh in 1274 BC, which is commemorated in bas-relief on many of his monuments. A thousand years later, Qin Shi Huang, the first ruler of united China, was so resolved to demonstrate his military prowess to the gods that he ordered himself to be buried alongside an army of terracotta troops. Romans gave military affairs a lot of attention, leaving behind numerous treatises and works on the topic as well as numerous elaborately sculpted triumphal arches and victory columns.

Concept of internal security

The state's ability to carry out its duties depends heavily on internal security. Protecting life and developing laws that would improve citizen wellbeing are fundamental functions of the state. If law and order cannot be maintained, the state cannot fulfil its first fundamental purpose. Internal security is therefore a crucial component of national growth and security. Furthermore, the problem of internal security is so important to nations and national leaders that they are willing to risk everything in order to defend or protect the security of their countries. Walter Lippman noted that a country is safe to the degree that its fundamental rights—life, property, and liberty—are not at risk. Internal security also alludes to the necessity of ensuring the Nation-State's survival through the practice of diplomatic, military, and political authority. While outlining his grand

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strategy, President Olusegun Obasanjo stated that the main goal of national security should be to strengthen the Federal Republic of Nigeria, reduce crime and corruption, promote genuine development, progress, and growth, and enhance citizen welfare (Attah, 2006). The military services are typically given this duty. However, the internal component of national security never receives much attention or funding; the Nigerian government does not have any clearly stated internal security policies. It has depended on impromptu actions, a fire squad strategy, excessive use of force, road blockages, and persuasion that is frequently ignored. And this helps to explain why the nation's domestic security has become so fragile. For instance, despite the catastrophic effects of armed theft on Nigeria's socioeconomic development, the call for a national summit on internal security has not yet been included in national debate. Security generally refers to the absence of risks or dangers, safety, or the capacity of the State to uphold its core principles, safeguard its lawful interests, and improve the welfare of its citizens. As a result, threats to property and life, including those posed by armed robbers, Boko Haram attacks, civil unrest, roadblocks that imperil other drivers, and other diversions, are signs that there is a dearth of internal security.

Internal security, as used in this research, refers to actions taken by domestic security forces like the police, customs, and immigration services, among others, to limit threats to national security that originate domestically. These dangers frequently involve dangerous situations involving riots, protests, strikes, communal disputes, terrorism, and the like, which typically do not come under the military's constitutional responsibilities. (International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces, 2002). For instance, it is the responsibility of the Police to uphold the rule of law and order in the community. The Police Act's Section 4 lists the basic responsibilities of the police as upholding law and order, protecting people and property, and properly enforcing all laws and rules that fall under their purview. A nation's internal disputes are handled by Internal Security Operations (ISOPs). Conflicts between communities and ethnic groups, religion disputes, and most lately acts of terrorism in Nigeria have made participation in ISOPs necessary.

Theoretical framework

The research, which is based on the integration theory created by military sociologist Morris Janowitz, centers on the military's professional standing and shifting social position. He sees the military as a career with established boundaries, guidelines, and norms of conduct. (Janowitz, 1960). He claims that civilian control of the military can only be accomplished when the military is integrated into society and the political decision-making process. This ensures that the military stays deferential to the rule of law. To prevent the military from developing a subculture and running the danger of becoming a state-within-the-state, Janowitz suggests that similar civilian, social, institutional, and cultural norms must exist (Lambert, 2009). He makes a number of reasons for why it is important to guarantee civil authority over the military. One of these factors is the shifting nature of security issues, which has led to an increase in the use of the military in law enforcement capacities. As a result, the distinction between policing and military duties as well as between peace and conflict is blurred in a number of states where the military is used in a domestic capacity. He anticipated that the military would play a larger part in law enforcement and eventually serve as the backup source of final legitimate force (Janowitz, 1960). Due to this, it is essential that the military upholds and supports society's democratic ideals while also respecting the authority bestowed upon government leaders. The military will be more dedicated to accomplishing the political objectives of the state where it supports the democratic values of society. (Janowitz, 1977). Again, this depends on the relative strength of the armed and civilian spheres. This can be troublesome, particularly in weak and autocratic states where the military is dissatisfied with the civilian government and exerts excessive control over political decision-making. (Auma-Osolo, 1980).

Due to their internal role and significance in ensuring political stability and security, military officials who become more politically aware subject the state to the risk of domestic military involvement in politics. When the officer corps is unhappy with the decisions or actions of civilian political officials, it becomes more and more motivated to take political power. This is especially true in nations with weak political structures and organizations and nations where civilian dominance is not institutionalized. The modern military commander is oriented toward maximizing his impact in politics and/or policy, as noted correctly by Perlmutter & Bennett in 1980. Therefore, because military leaders are familiar with political decision-making procedures, it is simple to use the flaws and failures of civilian leaders to advance personal interests, unless this is restrained (Feaver, 2003). From a different perspective, although Janowitz's concept of constabulary forces seems pertinent given that it relates to the use of the military in constabulary duties, it ignores parts of civil-military relations that deal with the interaction of the military with the populace. This covers things like the prevalence of military errors and abuses, which have been seen in a number of domestic security and peacekeeping missions. Taking Nigeria as an example, since the nation's independence in 1960, the military has participated in a number of domestic security and law enforcement missions (Okoli & Orinya, 2013; Dambazau, 2014). Given that Nigeria has been governed by the military for about 29 years, it has also played a significant role

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in governance (Ojo, 2006; Omede, 2012; Adeakin, 2015). The military has not, however, internalized societal principles that support civilian authority, respect for the law, or democratic values. (Agbu, 2004; Amnesty International, 2015). According to how I interpret Janowitz, he disregarded how the military's expertise and military culture can militarize the state and impact how they carry out police-like duties.

Military abuses, militarism, the militarization of society, and the infringement of citizens' human rights and civil freedoms rank among the main objections to using the military domestically (Nwolise, 2007; Odoemene, 2012). Problems frequently occur because military instruction and battle orientation are inappropriate for use in law enforcement and crowd management (Weiss, 2012). Additionally, even though it can manage masses, the military is still primarily a force used to fight battles and is very different from the police (Weiss, 2012). Its fundamental and most crucial ability is the capacity to disable, destroy, and cause the adversary great suffering (Gray, 2007). This explains the many difficulties and inconsistencies encountered when it is used internally, particularly when using force is involved. This can have an impact on the military's credibility and connection with the populace in states where victims of military abuse and excesses are not entitled to legal recourse. This leads one to the conclusion that, particularly in authoritarian states or states with weak civic control agencies, neither the separationist nor the integration theories are adequate to explain domestic security.

The nature of internal security in Nigeria

Communal bloodshed, threats, and significant domestic unrest have persisted in Nigeria since it gained independence from Britain on 1 October 1960. Every region of the nation has been impacted (Odoma, 2014), frequently throwing it into chaos and endangering political safety as well as the delivery of necessary public products and services, such as security (Ujomu, 2015). Six geographic zones, each containing five or more States, split Nigeria. According to their physical location and population makeup, these regional zones show the spatial spread of all the States of Nigeria, including the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja. In the North Central and North West Zones, communal conflicts are widespread because religious and ethnic diversity is exploited by desperate politicians and numerous armed groups to cause a rift for political/economic gains (Osaghae & Suberu, 2005). This is made worse by ongoing attacks by herders (mostly nomadic Fulani) on the indigenous population, which is made up of Christians from numerous 'minority' ethnic groups. In the North-East Zone, where Muslim Hausa's and Fulani. Communal conflicts are widespread in the North Central and North West Zones as a result of numerous armed groups and desperate politicians using the diversity of religion and ethnicity to foment strife for political and economic gain (Osaghae & Suberu, 2005). This is worsened by incessant herders' (mostly, nomadic Fulani) attacks on indigenous population, comprising of Christians of numerous 'minority' ethnic groups. In the North-East Zone, where Muslim Hausa's and Fulani's dominate, religious fanaticism and terrorism pose the greatest security concerns for especially, the non-Hausa/Fulani Christian minority. In the South West Zone, criminal violence and electoral violence endanger security, economic and political equilibrium in the area. While serious security threats (the Biafra secession crisis, the Niger-Delta Militancy, the Boko Haram terrorism, and the communal violence and herdsman attacks in Plateau State) are currently raging in four of the six geopolitical zones, these challenges "have been worsening on a daily basis" since Nigeria returned to democratic rule (Dambazau, 2014: 65).

The Nigerian military and internal security operations

According to Elaigwu (2003), the Nigerian Military has played a significant role in crisis management in Nigeria ever since the country's freedom. He contends that three fundamental factors influence the strategies used by the Nigerian Military in domestic security operations: a) the use of minimal force principle; b) adversary weapons holding, his tactical methods, and habits; and c) the topography of the enemy's location (Elaigwu, 2003). On top of this, Elaigwu illustrates the limitations of military intervention in domestic crisis management by demonstrating how the dispatch of a military force in the Tiv division in 1960 was unable to prevent the outbreak of violence there in 1961. Further acts of violence between July and August 1964—which culminated in another military deployment in November 1964—were not deterred by a comparable use of military force in February 1964. He continues by saying that although Maitatsine was subjected to the entire weight of military might in Kano in 1980, neither this nor later displays of physical force were able to prevent incidents of this nature from occurring in Bullumkuttu, Rigasa, Jimeta-Yola, and Gombe in 1982, 1984, and 1985, respectively (Elaigwu, 2003). The recent past, however, is ignored because the research only covers the first 33 years of Nigeria's freedom. According to Akpan (2011), Nigerian history is rife with instances of the military being used to put down internal uprisings. When it interfered in the Tiv disturbance in 1964, the Nigerian military made its first known appearance in domestic affairs. Since then, in Akpan's opinion, Nigerian leaders have used the military in political situations even when there is no proof that such actions have been successful.

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He uses the Niger Delta as the most recent illustration of the use of the military as a crisis management tool. He comes to the conclusion that the Mad Man's Theory is satisfied by the excessive use of military force to previously considered disproportionate levels to a domestic crisis and the parties' objectives and contends that the military is unsuited for conflict resolution and crisis management in a domestic setting that requires political resolution (Akpan, 2011). Dode (2012) makes the case that members of the Nigerian Armed Forces have a history of conducting successful peacekeeping operations throughout the globe, citing Sierra Leone and Liberia as examples. However, their security and crisis management efforts in Nigeria do not appear to be following through on this track record. According to Dode, military actions taken to maintain domestic security in Nigeria have largely been ineffective in resolving civic unrest. They have primarily been employed to advance the interests of certain political leaders. Dode (2012) comes to the conclusion that encouraging the enlistment of military people to resolve civil disputes in a democracy is strategically risky. According to Animasawun (2013), the military's use for domestic security activities in strife areas of Nigeria is fraught with peculiar, frequently regionally specific difficulties.

Armed organizations in Nigeria, including the Odua People's Congress (OPC), the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), Boko Haram, and organizations engaged in sectarian violence in Jos, are classified as terrorist organizations by Akpaotor and Oromarehake (2013). Ocheche (2013) distinguishes between three types of terrorism in Nigeria: state terrorism, group (ethno religious), and externally influenced terrorism. All of these types of terrorism have continued to pose a serious threat to Nigeria's stability. It is argued that the liberal political space created by Nigeria's return to democracy in 1999 was the floodgate that released these militant elements. He cites the NM operations in Odi and Zaki Biam in 1999 and 2001, respectively, as examples of domineering military operations that directly impact a large number of civilians (Ocheche 2013). In Nigeria, ethnic paramilitary activity that includes kidnapping hostages, killing people, setting buildings on fire, robbing people, raping people, and maiming people is frequently classified as group terrorism. These acts have been carried out by organizations like the Odua People's Congress (OPC), the Movement for the Actualization of the Sovereign State of Biafra (MASSOB), the Egbesu Boys, the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), and the Bakassi Boys, among others. Terrorism that is externally affected occurs when terrorist acts are committed by people or organizations outside of Nigeria who have connections to or supporters there. Osakwe and Umoh (2013) look at the paradox that arises when Nigeria uses its military forces to fight terrorism. They point out that a key component of any counterinsurgency plan is ensuring the safety of the local and civilian people. Success in counterinsurgency, however, has frequently been arrested and given a dearth of specified within framework for the Nigerian Military. Confront, Build, and Transfer, which are carried out by a mixture of an attack force, a support force, and a security force, are the three concepts highlighted by the Nigerian Military as the cornerstone of any effective COIN. In order to face fortified strongholds and deny insurgents access to their havens, the military assault force is needed. Building the host society requires the support team. Then, in order to stop crime, transfer would be made to the public security troops. The Nigerian Army's discipline between 1960 and 1965 is examined by Osakwe (2013). The case made by Crevelde (1990) and Huntington is used to support the idea of expertise. Half a decade after Nigeria gained freedom, Osakwe (2001) focused solely on the administration, instruction, and training of the Nigerian Army in his study of professionalism in the Nigeria military. Superlatives and variables like discipline, loyalty, corporations, patriotism, and bravery are simple to use to describe the factors that contributed to professionalism in the Nigerian Army during the time period under consideration. Upon their exit in 1960, the British colonial officials greatly diminished what would be considered expertise. The degree to which this was intentional didn't seem to be thoroughly investigated. The residue of colonization is identified by Ouédraogo (2014) as a major barrier to professionalism in Africa, extending the debate across the entire continent. Ouédraogo (2014) contends that African armies were "built from the ashes of colonial forces," inheriting the colonial militaries' racial biases that led to a lack of professionalism. To offset traditionally more powerful ethnicities, minority ethnicities typically made up the majority of the imperial military forces. The development of post-independence armies was significantly impacted by this early ethnic prejudice. Military commanders from these ethnic minorities frequently led the surge of coups d'état that toppled some of the first post-independence governments.

In their 2014 study, Lipede and Osakwe, they look at violent disputes and military deployment in Nigeria. They contend that by performing tasks like enforcement and fighting, the NM has overextended itself. According to Lipede and Osakwe (2014), by 2013, nearly thirty of Nigeria's thirty-six states had signed on to the "military save the state" plan. All domestic security initiatives supported by state governments came to be known collectively as Operation Mesa. He analyzes both intricate and simpler operations, such as Operation Restore Hope and Operation Iron Fence (highway military patrols to ensure the safety of highways). This is in opposition to the Nigeria Police Force, which is legally responsible for upholding internal security and maintaining law and order. Furthermore, Lipede and Osakwe (2014) contend that using the military for

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law enforcement functions degrades military expertise. He comes to the conclusion that regular forces, as demonstrated in pertinent past contexts and the context of Nigeria, have not been known to thwart insurgent activities. Between 2009 and 2014, Odu (2014) analyzes the difficulties faced by the Military Joint Task Force (JTF) in counterterrorism activities. In the 1999 constitution, the Nigerian Military was given a dual duty that included both suppressing insurrection and protecting Nigeria from foreign attack. Odu (2014) goes on to claim that institutional mechanisms are used to accomplish collaboration between the NM and other security organizations. According to the research, the JTF faces a number of fundamental challenges, including a lack of strategic direction for inter-agency collaboration, poor technological intelligence tools, a lack of capacity, organizational limitations, and low levels of public support.

Mode of Operation of the military during Internal Security Operations

The Nigerian military has frequently participated in peacekeeping missions abroad and has received praise for its honourable behaviour on those occasions; two prime instances are Sierra Leone and Liberia. Why not, when it comes to internal security operations, is a mystery! One persistent issue that is cited as a weakness is the heavy handedness and insensitivity to the nature and traits of areas that are controlled by civilians (Dode, 2012). The Nigerian military's involvement in domestic security activities is characterized by a number of traits, the majority of which are detrimental. Below is a discussion on some modes of operation:

1. **Excessive use of force:** Excessive force is generally defined as force that is beyond what a reasonable and prudent law enforcement officer would use in the given situation. Article 51(5)(b) of the 1977 Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions forbids attacks that may be anticipated to result in incidental loss of civilian life, injury to civilians, damage to civilian objects, or a combination of these, which would be excessive in relation to the circumstances. There have been numerous allegations of excessive force being used by the military during domestic missions. The incident that is commonly referred to as the Odi Massacre serves as an example of this. a raid by the Nigerian military on the largely Ijaw-populated hamlet of Odi in Bayelsa State on November 20, 1999. The assault took place amid the Niger Delta conflict over native peoples' access to hydrocarbon resources and environmental protection. Twelve (12) Nigerian police officers were killed before the Massacre by a group of unruly teenagers close to the hamlet of Odi. On orders from the Federal government, the military attacked and raided the hamlet in what appeared to be an act of retaliation. The use of force in this assault was severe and extreme. Thousands of defenseless civilians, including women and children, were actually slain as a result. With the exception of the bank, the Anglican Church, and the Community Health Centre, every structure in the hamlet was obliterated, leaving it in an appalling state of ruin (Okoli & Orinya, 2013).
2. **Extra judicial killings:** Extrajudicial killings by the military have also been a feature of domestic security activities. In April 2013, the governor of Borno State, Kashim Shettima, claimed that a weekend confrontation between members of the Joint Task Force and insurgents in Baga resulted in the deaths of over 100 persons. The Red Cross reports that 187 people were slain in the fight, but the villagers claim they buried 185 victims (Ola, 2013). According to human rights watch, troops from the 23rd armoured brigade of the 3rd armoured division rounded up locals in Gbeji (in the Zaki Biam region of Benue State) during a military exercise that started on October 22, 2001, for what turned out to be a "ployed meeting." The soldiers forced the villagers to settle down on the ground, dividing them into men and women, and then opened fire on the males without discrimination (Human Right Watch, 2001). There have also been numerous allegations of extrajudicial executions carried out by the Nigerian military.
3. **Degrading treatment of citizens – rape, torture:** Soldiers reportedly extort citizens after intimidating them; it is now standard practice for soldiers to ask defaulting car drivers on the high way to do "frog jumps" as a form of punishment; women and girls are raped on a number of occasions whether or not during internal security operations; and soldiers reportedly extort citizens after intimidating them.
4. **Arbitrary arrest:** As an example, many young people were arbitrarily detained at Odi and Zaki Biam and falsely accused of planning the murder of security personnel, and several youths were detained at Onitsha and falsely accused of belonging to MASSOB (Okoli & Orinya, 2013). This is just one of many examples of how soldiers engaged in internal security operations detain people.

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Challenges of the military in internal security operations in Nigeria

The need for the military to adapt to the demands of domestic security operations is informed by the military's participation in civil operations. When working with civic activities, the military typically has trouble adjusting. The following are some places that have been identified as the root of these issues:

1. **Training:** Since the primary duty of the military is to protect the nation during times of war, as noted by the International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces (2002), military training is typically based on dealing the greatest amount of harm and destruction to their adversaries and defeating them in the shortest amount of time while adhering to the laws and regulations of armed conflict. Contrary to what is typically expected of troops in traditional conflict, internal security operations only call for caution and the use of minimal force. Because they are now preserving law and order among their own citizens in their own nation, the minimal force prerequisite is necessary.
2. The type of training that soldiers receive can be responsible for the military's arbitrary actions during domestic security missions. Therefore, the troops must receive the necessary instruction to manage internal activities. Lt. Gen. Onyeabo Ihejirika, the Nigerian Army's chief of staff, also recognized this reality, stating that the Nigerian Army must reorient its infrastructure training to accommodate for domestic security operations in support of civil authority (Utebor, 2010).
3. **Orientation:** This is a person's mind-set or point of view. According to a military perspective, any possible danger should be eliminated because it is an enemy. It's risky to operate internally with this kind of mentality. The defence used against internal "enemies" should be distinguished from the defence used against exterior attack.
4. The way the military is seen when asked to carry out domestic security missions is another problem. Some troops believe they have a loftier purpose than this, and some even believe they have been called upon because the police are unable and ineffective at upholding law and order. As a consequence, instead of assisting the civil authorities as required by section 217 of the 1999 Constitution, the military typically takes over police activities. The military ends up assuming the lead rather than assisting the police or other worried civic officials. This may lead to resentment and mistrust between the troops assigned to the interior operations and the police force participating in the operation. Unhealthy competition could result from this, which could ultimately compromise security efforts (International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces, 2002). The Nigerian Army has argued in favour of a unified method to coordinate Joint Task Force Operations in the nation because it would stop different heads of security agencies from enforcing order and reversing it (Radio Nigeria Ibadan Online, 2013).
5. **Equipment:** The soldiers engaged in domestic security activities frequently lack the necessary equipment. If their lives are in danger from a hostile mob, soldiers involved in internal operations who are only armed will surely use it. In Nigeria, a typical crowd can only have access to stones, not firearms. It will not be appropriate to use lethal tools, such as firearms, in this circumstance.
6. **Strategy and tactics:** Combat operations depend on military strategy and techniques. To achieve broad political and military goals, military actions are planned, coordinated, and generally led by strategy. By making quick choices about troop movements and the use of weapons in combat, tactics put strategy into action. In times of conflict, armies all over the globe utilize certain strategies and techniques. The goal, the attack, surprise, security, unity of command, economy of force, mass, and manoeuvre are some of the most frequently mentioned concepts. History records that the Allied forces ultimately concurred on the goal of defeating Germany first with a straight offensive against the European continent, providing a renowned example that exemplifies most of these principles. They successfully gathered their forces in England, misled Germany about the invasion's entry point, gathered information on the location of German forces, and launched the massive operation known as Operation Overlord under the combined command of Gen. Dwight D. Eisenhower (Military Strategy and Tactics, Accessed April 04, 2023) (<http://www.molossia.org/milacademy/strategy.html>).
7. Another strategy is the Envelopment stratagem, which involves the surprise apparition of enemy forces on a flank or from behind. If a force is surrounded, it can be starved of provisions or come under assault from any direction (Azinge, 2013). Dealing with a hostile crowd of civilians in a riot situation requires a completely different approach from an attack on an enemy position in conventional warfare. There is a need to adapt to the smaller scale of operations and the tactical mobility required. It has been agreed that internal conflicts do not always require all these tactics that soldiers typically employ (International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces, 2002).

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Conclusion

According to the study, there are many different ways that contemporary conflicts and violence manifest, and these ways are frequently determined by the actors and their justifications for using violence. This means that both state and non-state actors perpetrate contemporary violence, and these non-state actors could take the form of a militia, an insurgent, terrorist groups, or organized criminal and transnational criminal organizations. The issue with armed group actions, as seen in Kaduna State, is that they are hard to put down, and the authorities are powerless to stop the spread of armed violence. Numerous African police forces that are understaffed and poorly prepared to deal with their dangers are overwhelmed by armed groups that use irregular, sustained violence against government forces and civilian organizations. As a result, many African countries now routinely use the military to quell the violence and conflicts that these organizations incite. This is the scenario in Nigeria, where several regions of the nation continue to experience incidents of persistent and ongoing violent conflict and violence. This is problematic, especially when the military is generally abusive and engaged in numerous predatory activities that violate the human rights of the populace and further their sense of insecurity. Despite the military's acceptance as the most powerful organ of the state with the superior coercive force to suppress the threats and violence posed by armed groups.

Recommendations

The study made the following recommendations:

1. Improved civic authority over the military is required at all levels of government. Compliance would increase if the National Assembly, who are the representatives of the people, increased its parliamentary supervision of the military and its adherence to the rules governing its tasks. The disclosure of the military's standards of engagement for all domestic security operations could also fall under this category. The advantage of this is that it will increase accountability, guarantee compliance, and function as the benchmark for evaluating the actions and performance of people assigned for each ISOP in society. Without it, it is challenging to decide which staff actions are acceptable, when force should be used against citizens, and to what degree force can be used against a riotous or protesting civilian group.
2. The function of an impartial military ombudsman who can successfully step in to address cases of military mistreatment is another crucial factor to take into account. While the National Human Rights Commission of Nigeria currently handles comparable tasks as an ombudsman, an independent military investigator who is focused on military abuse problems would be more helpful. In order to properly handle the issue, it is imperative to give the daily presence of the military in society and the high frequency of military misuse primary focus. Additionally, given that the military is on active duty in many regions of the nation, this action may help to increase public confidence in this government entity and raise its standing and authority.

References

- Abdullahi, M.M., Wika, P.N. & Abdul-Qadir, U.A. (2016). An Overview of Public Perception of Internal Security. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 21(5):8–28.
- Agbu, O. (2004). *Ethnic Militias and the Threat to Democracy in Post-Transition Nigeria*. Uppsala: Nordiska Afrikainstitutet.
- Akpan, O. (2011). *The Niger Delta Question and the Peace Plan*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books.
- Akpotor, A. S. & Oromareghake, P.B. (2013). "Terrorism and Insecurity in the Nigerian State: The Challenge." In *Internal Security Management in Nigeria: A Study in Terrorism and Counter-Terrorism*, edited by Ozoemenam Mbachau and Umar M. Bature, 67-86. Kaduna: Medusa Academic Publishers Limited.
- Amnesty International. (2015). *Stars on Their Shoulders. Blood on Their Hands: War Crimes Committed By the Nigerian Military*. London: Amnesty International. [Online], Available: <https://www.amnesty.org/download/Documents/AFR4416572015ENGLISH.PDF>.
- Animasawun, G. A. (2013). The Military and Internal Security Operations in Nigeria's Fourth Republic: Rethinking Security for Positive Peace in Maiduguri, Nigeria. *Peace Research* 44/45, 2 (1): 113-134.
- Auma-Osoto, A. (1980). Objective African Military Control. A New Paradigm in Civil-Military Relations. *Journal of Peace Research*, 17(1):29–46.
- Azinge, E. (2013). Military in internal security operations: Challenges and prospects. A Paper Presented at the Nigerian Bar Association 53rd Annual General Conference, 28th August, TINAPA Calabar, Nigeria.
- Baker, B. (2010). *Nonstate Policing: Expanding the Scope for Tackling Africa's Urban Violence*. Washington, DC: Africa Center for Strategic Studies.

Qualitative study on military and ... (Ushie, et. al., 2023) DOI:

- Bigo, D. (2000). When Two Become One: Internal and External Securitization in Europe. In *International Relations Theory and the Politics of European Integration: Power, Security and Community*. M. Kelstrup & M.C. Williams, Eds. London: Routledge.
- Buzan, B. (1991). *People, States and Fear: An Agenda for International Security Studies in the Post-Cold War Era*. 1st ed. New York: Harvester Wheatsheaf.
- CKN NIGERIA (2013). "Nigerian Soldiers rape Women in Abuja". <http://www.cknnigeria.com/2013/01/nigerian-soldiers-rape-women-in-abuja.html> accessed on the 24 August 2022.
- Collier, P. & Hoeffler, A. (2002). On the Incidence of Civil War in Africa. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 46(1):13–28.
- Dambazau, A.S. (2014). Nigeria and Her Security Challenges. *Harvard International Review*, 65–70.
- Dode, R. (2012). Nigerian Security Forces and the Management of Internal Conflict in the Niger Delta: Challenges of Human Security and Development. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 1 (3): 409-418.
- Elaigwu, V. A. (2003). *The Military and the Management of Civil Crises in Nigeria. 1960-1993*. Kaduna: Nigerian Defence Academy Press.
- Falola, T. & Heaton, M. M. (2008). *A history of Nigeria*. Cambridge University Press.
- Fearon, J. & Laitin, D. (2003). Ethnicity, Insurgency, and Civil War. *American Political Science*, 97(1):75–90.
- Feaver, P.D. (2003). *Armed Servants: Agency, Oversight, and Civil-Military Relations*. Cambridge MA: Harvard University Press.
- Gray, C.S. (2007). Irregular Warfare: One Nature, Many Characters. *Strategic Studies Quarterly*. 1(2):24–26.
- Gurr, T.R., Marshall, M.G. & Khosla, D. (2000). *Peace and Violent Conflict, 2001: A Global Survey of Armed Conflicts, Self-Determination Movements, and Democracy*. College Park, MD: Center for International Development and Conflict Management.
- Human Rights Watch (2001)
- Iheanacho, A.C. & Iheanacho, A. A. (2012). *Research methodology for social sciences and education*. Ibadan: Stirling-Horden Publishers Ltd.
- International Committee of the Red Cross United Relations with Armed and Security Forces (2002). *The law of armed conflict internal security operations*.
- Janowitz, M. (1960). *The Professional Soldier: A Social and Political Portrait*. Glencoe, ILL: Free Press.
- Janowitz, M. (1977). *Military Institutions and Coercion in the Developing Nations: The Military in the Political Development of New Nations*. Chicago & London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Jordan, D.; Kiras, J. D.; Lonsdale, D. J.; Speller, I.; Tuck, C. & Walton, C. D. (2016). *Understanding modern warfare (Second ed.)*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lambert, A. 2009. *Democratic Civilian Control of Armed Forces in the Post-Cold War Era*. Berlin: LIT Verlag.
- Lioe, K.E. (2011). *Armed Forces in Law Enforcement Operations? The German and European Perspective*. Heidelberg, Dordrecht, London & New York: Springer.
- Lipede, A. & Osakwe, C. (2014). "Violent Conflicts and Troop Deployment in Nigeria since 2009." In *Perspectives on Contemporary Nigeria: Essays in Honour of Professor A. Bolaji Akinyemi*, edited by Ichimi Godwin, 269-192. Abuja: Salwin Nigeria Ltd.
- Mark, J. J. (2009). "War in Ancient Times". *World History Encyclopedia*.
- Military Strategy and Tactics <http://www.molossia.org/milacademy/strategy.html> accessed on the 24th of August 2022.
- Nwolise, O.B.C. (2007). Military Assistance to Civil Authority as a Constitutional Duty of the Nigerian Armed Forces: Sources of Public Agonies and Outcries, Bad Military Image, and Their Challenges for Political Leadership, Military Command and Professionalism. In *Peace Support Operations, Command and Professionalism: Challenges for the Nigerian Armed Forces in the 21st Century*. O.A. Ogomudia, Ed. Ibadan: Gold Press.
- Ochoche, S. A. (2013). "Counter-Terrorism Strategy for Nigeria in the Twenty First Century." In *Internal Security Management in Nigeria: A Study in Terrorism and Counter-Terrorism*, edited by Ozoemenam Mbachu and Umar M. Bature, 343-359. Kaduna, Nigeria: Medusa Academic Publishers Limited.
- Odoemene, A. (2012). The Nigerian Armed Forces and Sexual Violence in Ogoniland of the Niger Delta Nigeria, 1990–1999. *Armed Forces & Society*. 38(2):225–251.
- Odu, O. I. (2014). "Challenges of the Joint Task Force in Counter-Terrorism Operations in Nigeria, 2009-2014." In *Nigerian Defence and Security: Essays in Commemoration of Nigerian Defence Academy Golden Jubilee*, edited by Ojong Echum Tangban, Chukwuma C. Osakwe, Sunday O. Okeniyi, and Henry E. Ayamasawe, 577-598. Kaduna: Nigerian Defence Academy Press.

Qualitative study on military and ... (Ushie, et. al., 2023) DOI:

- Ogah, P. (2011). Law and Security in Nigeria: The Role of the Military. In *Law and Security in Nigeria*. E. Azinge, F. Bello, & Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, Eds. Lagos: Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies: 70–89.
- Ojo, E.O. (2006). Taming the Monster: Demilitarization and Democratization in Nigeria. *Armed Forces & Society*, 32(2):254–272.
- Okoli, A. & Orinya, S. (2013). Evaluating the Strategic Efficacy of Military Involvement in Internal Security Operations (ISOPs) in Nigeria. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, (9) 6: 23
- Okoli, A.C. & Okpaleke, F.N. (2014). Cattle rustling and dialectics of security in northern Nigeria”. *International Journal of Liberal Arts and Social Sciences*, 2(3): 109–17.
- Okumu, W. & Ikelegbe, A. (2010). Introduction: Towards Conceptualisation and Understanding of the Threats of Armed Non-State Groups to Human Security and the State in Africa. In *Militias, Rebels and Islamist Militants: Human Insecurity and State Crises in Africa*. W. Okumu & A. Ikelegbe, Eds. Tshwane: Institute for Security Studies: 1–44.
- Okumu, W. & Ikelegbe, A. 2010c. Confronting the Threats of Armed Non-State Groups to Human Security and the State in Africa. In *Militias, Rebels and Islamist Militants: Human Insecurity and State Crises in Africa*. W. Okumu & A. Ikelegbe, Eds. Tshwane: Institute for Security Studies. 437–468.
- Ola, A. (2013). “Borno Governor says ‘over 100 people’ killed in Baga; orders distribution of relief materials” .Premium Times Newspaper online . <http://premiumtimesng.com/news/130894-borno-governor-says-over-100-people-killed-in-baga-orders-distribution-of-relief-materials.html> accessed on 24 August 2022.
- Olaniyan, A. & Yahaya, A. (2016). Cows, bandits and violent conflicts: Understanding cattle rustling in Northern Nigeria”. *African Spectrum*,3: 93-105.
- Omede, A.J. (2012). The Nigerian Military: Analysing Fifty Years of Defence and Internal Military and Fifty Years of Internal Security Operations in Nigeria (1960-2010). *Journal of Social Sciences*. 33(3):293–303.
- Orodho, A.J. & Kombo, D.K. (2002). Research methods. Nairobi, Kenyatta institute of learning.
- Osakwe, C. & Umoh, U.E . (2013). “The Military and Counterinsurgency Operations in Nigeria.” In *Internal Security Management in Nigeria: A Study in Terrorism and Counter-Terrorism*, edited by Ozoemenam Mbachu and Umar M. Bature, 391-406. Kaduna, Nigeria: Medusa Academic Publishers Limited.
- Ouedraogo, E. (2014). Advancing Military Professionalism in Africa. *Research Paper* No. 6. Africa Centre of Strategic Studies, Washington, DC.
- Perlmutter, A. & Bennett, V.P. 1980. Introduction. In *The Political Influence of the Military: A Comparative Reader*. A. Perlmutter & V.P. Bennett, Eds. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press.
- Peterside, Z.B. (2014). The Military and Internal Security in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(27):1301–1307.
- Radio Nigeria Ibadan Online (2013). Nigerian Army advocates centralized system for JTF operations. (Radio Nigeria Ibadan online) <http://www.radionigeriaibadan.com/nigerian-army-advocates-centralized-system-for-jtf-operations> accessed on the 23rd August 2013.
- Sarkees, M.R., Wayman, F.W. & Singer, D.J. (2003). Inter-State, Intra-State, and Extra-State Wars: A Comprehensive Look at Their Distribution over Time, 1816–1997. *International Studies Quarterly*. 47(1):49–70.
- Schneckener, U. 2006. Fragile Statehood, Armed Non-State Actors and Security Governance. In *Private Actors and Security Governance*. A. Bryden & M. Caparin, Eds. Geneva: DCAF/LitVerlag.
- Schneider, G., Banholzer, L. & Albarracin, L. 2015. Ordered Rape: A Principal – Agent Analysis
- Shettima, A.G. & Tar, U.A. (2008). Farmer-pastoralist conflicts in West Africa: Exploring the causes and consequences. *Information, Society and Justice*, 1(2): 163-184.
- Stewart, F. (2002). Root Causes of Violent Conflict in Developing Countries. *British Medical Journal*, 324(7333):342–345.
- Stewart, F. (2004). Development and Security. *Conflict, Security & Development*, 4(3):261–288.
- Thompson, P.G. (2014). *Armed Groups: The 21st Century Threat*. London: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Utebor, S. (2010). Internal security: Army to refocus training. NBF News, Wednesday, 8.
- Vinci, A. (2008). Anarchy, Failed States, and Armed Groups: Reconsidering Conventional Analysis. *International Studies Quarterly*, 52(2):295–314.
- Vreĭ, F. (2010). Current and Future Trends in Insurgency. In *South Africa and Contemporary Counterinsurgency: Roots, Practices, Prospects*. D. Baker & E. Jordan, Eds. Claremont: UCT Press.
- Weiss, T. (2012). Fighting Wars or Controlling Crowds? The Case of the Czech Military Forces and the Possible Blurring of Police and Military Functions. *Armed Forces & Society*. 39(3):450–466.